

**COMMON PROFESSIONAL ADMINISTRATIVE TECHNIQUES OF FORMAL
ORGANIZATIONAL COMMUNICATION THROUGH FILE MINUTING IN
COLLEGES OF EDUCATION (COEs) IN NIGERIA: A REVIEW**

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Abstract

Organization use administrative skills. It mostly use official form of communication. File minuting forms part of day to day organizational communication. However, researchers have not done much in this aspect of communication, more especially in Nigeria. This study explored file minuting as administrative skills for official organizational communication in COEs using Review of related literatures method. The review revealed that file minuting have ethical “don’ts” like Never continue letter numbering from a page to another page nor number paragraphs with alphabets (a, b, c, etc); never number the first paragraph nor number the second paragraph with one (1), but with 2 (as it is assumed that the first unnumbered paragraph has a silent number 1) among others. Equally, administrative skills include organizing and maintening filing systems; teamwork and interpersonal skills; problem solving skills; decision making; technology and software and time management skills respectively. The paper recommends that management of COEs in Nigeria should make sure that these ethical “dont’s” are avoided and use administrative skills effectively.

Keywords: Administrative techniques, Organizational communication, Official communication, File minuting and File minuting communication.

Introduction

In every organization or establishment, there are administrators. Therefore tertiary institutions like Colleges of Education also have administrators. Administrators in organization communicate within themselves to enable them work harmoniously to enable the organization achieve its set goals and objectives. Communication within the organization becomes important to create a common understanding of the information presented to each other for the progress of the organization. The day-to-day engagements and transactions in organization have to be communicated from one another and from one department to another within the same organization. These communications are often done in writing through minutes, letters, memorandums, reports, etc. These minutes in files move from one table to the other. It moves between officials from top to bottom or from bottom to top to inform, educate, direct and taje decision that can be evident for future reference. In the course of official communications as bureaucracy entails, stages must be followed, hence minuting /communication takes place among the officials concerned. The administrative ommunications or minuting sometimes involves a great deal of jargons.

Conceptual Clarifications

The purpose of this study is to use conceptual secondary sources to review the common professional administrative techniques for file minuting organizational communication in COEs using secondary expository research method or literature review to review related conceptual literature on common administrative techniques or skills of organizational communication. This method is used because Snyder (2019), explains that literature review is more or less systematic way of collecting and synthesizing previous research. This is because a well conducted review as a research method creates a firm foundation for advancing knowledge and facilitating theory development. It is an excellent way of synthesizing research findings to show evidence on a meta-level and to uncover areas in which more research is needed, which is a critical component of creating a theoretical frameworks and building conceptual models.

Basically, some conceptual clarifications are presented below:

Administrative techniques: This refers to skills and strategies that administrators to perform their administrative tasks effectively.

Organizational communication: This refers to channels or forms of communication that occur between or among people working within an organization to achieve organizational goals.

Official communication: In this context, official communication refers to goal oriented, explicitly stated and function related communication that takes place within an official or formal organization.

File minuting: This, in this context refers to recording important details of discussions and decisions made regarding a case or matter within a file, essentially to serve as future evidence within an organization

File minuting communication: This refers to communication through recording important details of discussions and decisions made regarding a case or matter within a file, essentially to serve as future evidence within an organization

Review of Conceptual Background

Administrative Techniques or Skills

Bhagwan and Bhushan (2010) opined that administration in a modern welfarist state stands out not only to protect and restrain but has also been seen to foster and promote. That administration is the determined action taken in pursuit of a conscious purpose; a systematic ordering of affairs and the calculated use of resources aimed at making those things happen

which we want to make happen. It is therefore the organization and use of men and materials to accomplish common goals.

In every organization or establishment, there are administrators. Therefore tertiary institutions also have administrators. The administrators in tertiary institution are divided into Seven (7) categories, thus: 1. Policy group 2. Career Administrators 3. Professionals in Administration 4. Academic Administrators 5. Academics in Administration 6. Classroom Administrator 7. Chartered Professional Administrators (Msheliza, 2024; Bello, 2024). While Msheliza (2024) listed first 5, Bello (2024) increased it to 7.

1. **The policy group:** Members of Governing Council, Academic Board, Principal Officers as stipulated by statute: Provosts, Deputy Provost, Registrar and College Librarian.
2. **The Career Administrators:** The “Professional or Pure Administrators” who are the officers on the career path to Registrarship whose duty is to keep the day-to-day administration of the College on the move. They serve as Secretaries to various College Committees and must provide the facilitating duties that ensure the effectuation of the core objectives of the College. Expectedly, this is all of us in this conference.
3. **The Professionals in Administration:** Specialists with some particular skills or professions who find themselves in some administrative positions in the College. They include Accountants, Engineers, Doctors, Lawyers, Academic Planners, Public Relations Personnel, etc.
4. **The Academic Administrators:** Teaching staff who are from time-to-time appointed to administrative positions such as Deans, Heads of Departments, Directors of Centers, etc. While they remain teachers and researchers, they are involved in the day-to-day administration of their various Faculties/Schools/Departments and Centers and the College at large.
5. **The Academics in Administration:** Members of the teaching staff who are appointed to serve from time-to-time on various policy-making Committees of Council, Academic Board and other Committees of the College.
6. **Classroom Administrator:** Members of Academic staff that manage students in their classes
7. **Chartered Professional Administrators:** These include Policy group, Career Administrators, Professionals in Administration, Academic Administrators and Academics in Administration who are fully chartered members of any of the Administrative Professional bodies.

Profession and Professional

There are certain elements and characteristics expected as foundation for entry into a particular profession or professional bodies. This encompasses a range of behaviors, skills, and ethical standards. According to Adebayo, (2023); Adetayo (2024); Msheliza (2024), a professional is supposed to possess these elements and characteristics apart from academic qualification. These include the following: a. Mastering of an esoteric (specialized) body of knowledge usually acquired via academic qualification. For instance, a degree; b. Displaying skills through handling job professionally with competency, effectiveness and efficiency using experience; c. Displaying behaviour through integrity, honesty, transparency, confidentiality and accountability; d. Displaying loyalty through obedience, true followership and respect.

Others include e. Displaying mentorship through providing invaluable insights and guidance mentees, using one's wealth of experience and wisdom; f. Displaying competency through skills, knowledge and expertise to perform one's duties effectively; g. Provision of continuous professional education; h. Existence as professional society/body (being registered); i. Accreditation/operational certification/licensing and j. Code of ethics/ethical standards through adherence to ethical standards.

The above elements can be seen in administration. Therefore administration can be placed as a profession and if a person fulfils being inducted as a member of a chartered professional body, then he qualifies as a professional administrator.

Administrative Techniques Skills

Keiling, H (2024) Administrative skills to build for professional growth. Defines administrative skills as qualities that can enhance administrative job progress that will lead to achieving organizational goals.

Keiling (2024), explains that administrative techniques or skills include organizational skills like organizing and maintaining filing systems, records, and databases, making phone calls and scheduling meetings, writing memos, letters, minuting and communications; communication skills like active listening skills, writing skills, speaking skills and reading skills; teamwork and interpersonal skills like effective interaction skills; problem solving skills like ability to identify problems, ability to produce best solutions to the identified problem and confident decision making and communicating decision effectively; technology and software skills like using computer and internet; time management skills where you have to manage time effectively to be succeed respectively.

Organizational Communication

Organization communication to Bhagwan & Bhushan (2010) refers to sending and receiving information about the organizational between individuals and parties directly involved in organizations and outside the organization. This is because communication is one important thing to support the success of the organization both in improving organizational performance and organizational adaptation to any changes in the existing environment. Through good communication between individuals and parties directly involved in organizations and outside the organization, organizations can obtain the necessary information.

Adamu, Manu, Saadu & Isah (2020) explains that organizational communication could be verbal or non-verbal, formal or informal. Official communication could be conducted through: letter writing, memorandum, reports, minuting, meetings, telephone conversations, e-mails, fax, walkie-talkie, etc. The common and most frequent methods of official communication within an organization are the letter writing and minuting which are being done on routine basis.

Organizational Communication through File Minuting

Communication is the act of conveying information for creating a shared understanding. It's something that humans do every day. In other words, Communication is the activity of conveying information through the exchange of thoughts, messages, or information, as by speech, visuals, signals, writing, or behavior (Bhagwan & Bhushan, 2010).

Communication in an office is an essential means of sending and receiving of information between one officer and another to discuss the business of government and arrive at a particular decision that is considered the best in the interest of government and the public. Therefore, every aspect of doing a particular job may entail engaging in one form of official communication or another. Communication in whatever form is a sure way of getting things done. Things cannot move or change without communication.

According to Wikipedia (2024), organizational communication is the channel and forms of communication that occur between or among people working within an organization to achieve organizational goals. It is communication that takes place between people who are working towards common goals within an organization. It consists of the interactions that take place for the purpose of working together towards these goals or conducting business or organization in general. It involves interpersonal communication, intergroup communication, written communication corporate communication, strategic communication, business communication, internal and external communication, communication management, upward, downward and horizontal communication.

Official or Formal Communication

Gomez & Dailey (2017), defined Formal communication according to as goal-oriented, explicitly stated, function related communication that flows through the hierarchy, follows prescribed norms, and transcends time and space.

Formal communication is function related because the communication is addressed to the organizational function rather than the person occupying the organizational role. In other words, the individual who occupies the role is not as relevant as the individual's position in the organization.

Official or formal communication according to Sikri (2014) is the name given to the type of exchange of information between or among officials within a formal or officials organization to help achieve organization.

Robert (2023), sees that official communication refers to communication made by a member of an official organization within a formal organization.

Nwamaka (2014), explains that communication is said to be formal, if the dissemination of information, messages and ideas are done according to prescribed or fixed rules and customs. Such Communication is usually very rigid and follows definite pattern and it is official in nature. It may be oral or written, vertical or horizontal. That the various means of carrying out formal communications in an organisation are as follows: a. Telephone b. Computers c. Postal system d. written instructions in i. memos, ii. letters, iii. minutes, iv. notice boards, d. company's magazines, journals, newsletters, pay slips etc., e. broadcast messages over public address systems. f. briefs in meetings addressed by senior officers to subordinates. g. inter-departmental committees. h. interviews to give instruction or information or to review a subordinate's performance. i. joint committees of management and employees. j. suggestion boxes. k. questionnaires.

According Nwamak (2014), further explains that informal Communication. It is described as any interaction or relationship which exists in any organization which is unofficial or unplanned. It may also be viewed as messages conveyed through gestures, facial expressions, body movements, the intonations or emphasis we give to words, and the physical distance between the sender and receiver. That means of informal communication are as follows: a. Conversations between employees at all levels. b. a private telephone conversation to facilitate the speedy accomplishment of a task in an organisation. This is usually based on personal or friendly relationship between the officers in the organisation. c. cartoons in the notice boards. d. secret signs and gestures warning other officers of the approach of an officer that is not supposed to be privy to the information or of the approach of a senior manager. e. grapevines or rumours.

Sikri (2014) explains that directions of organizational communication could be downward, upward or horizontal. a. Downward communication: Downward communication is communication from top to bottom. b. Upward communication: Upward communication is the direction from bottom to top. c. Horizontal communication: This is a communication direction that flows among officers at the same position, rank or positions e.g. a communication among Directors or HODs, etc.

Minutes and File Minuting

Minutes, according to Adamu, Manu, Saadu & Gaya (2020) are views, opinions, advice, information or directives expressed in writing during the course of day- to- day work in the office. Minutes are usually enclosed in paper jackets, known as files. The files are bearing different names, reference numbers and meant for different subject matters. Minutes may also be defined as communication in writing, usually in files, between two or more officials. Minutes are normally used to consider and settle matter or to direct what action may be taken in a given circumstance (ASCON, 2015 & Civil Service Manual, 2019).

Minutes according to Adamu (2017), is communication in writing, usually in files, between two or more officials. Minutes are submission of facts in concise form, while minuting is an act of writing a minute. It is different from minutes of meeting which are recorded in a special way. They are different from minutes of meetings which are recorded in a special way. Internal minutes are normally only used when addressing officers within the same ministry or department.

Minuting to Braji (2019), is the central means of communication in both public and private organizations. Files move from one table to another conveying or reporting issues, views opinions, information, recommendations, decisions, or directives in minutes, form, Thus, minutes express the views and ideas of officers in a formal organization. Minutes should be in a clear, concise, brief and legible and informative manner.

Wikipedia (2011), defines minutes as views, opinions, advices, information of activities expressed in writing during the course of day-to-day work in the office. Minutes is communication in writing usually in files, between two or more officials in an organization. Minutes are usually enclosed in a paper jacket called file.

Minutes, to Nwamaka (2014), is communication in writing between two or more officials in an organization. Minutes are normally used to consider and settle matters or to direct what action may be taken in a circumstance.

Muniting in a File is in form of views, opinions, advices, information or directives expressed in writing during the course of day- to- day work in the office (Adebayo, 2000).

Filing

Having discussed the concept of registry and file, it is good to delve into filing which is the transmission of administrative communication.

Filing to Gambo and Manu (2021), is a systematic arrangement of keeping administrative correspondence and records which enable quick reference whenever needed in the future. It is the placing of documents and papers in acceptable containers according to some predetermined arrangements so that any time required, it can be located with ease.

According to them, a good filing system should have the following requirements: i. The system should be kept simple to reduce errors and to facilitate all employees' use of the system; ii. Files should contain information which is linked to the activities and functions which they document; iii. The system should have a structured numeric or alphanumeric referencing system in which each element corresponds with a function of the file title to a maximum of four elements. Types of file referencing systems include: alphabetical; numerical; alphanumeric; and keyword.

Kailes and Enders (2014), classified filing into five methods as follows:

1. Filing by subject/category. It is a system where files and folders of documents are arranged in accordance with their subjects. It therefore uses alphabetical order of the subjects;
2. Filing in alphabetical order. It is a system where files and folders of documents are arranged in order of alphabets of the names of the persons or institutions concern with such files. This method is easy to understand, time saving, very efficient for retrieval and does not require separate index;
3. Filing by numbers/numerical order. This type is a system of organizing records through the use of numbers that appear on the materials. It deals with classifying of files using numbers as headings. Numerical filing is a method in which files and folders are arranged in order of number. All files and folders are classified and given separate number. In this type of filing alphabetical index is required. It includes name, address, phone number, subject and other information along with number. This can be used for large organization;
4. Filing by places/geographical order. It is a system where files and folders of documents are arranged in accordance to the geographical location of firms, organization or persons. Under this, the name of places are written in the files and arranged in alphabetical order or numbers. It is used in multi- national companies with branches located in various countries, states or locations;

5. Filing by dates/chronological order. This is the filing system where files and folders of documents are arranged in order of their date, day, and time. This sequence could be according to the date the documents were received, or date and time the files were created. In this case, the most recent date is in front of or on top of the previous ones. This can only be suitable for specific things, like receipts. It is suitable for small organization.

It is expensive for smaller organization

File Minuting Symbols and Abbreviations

Symbols: X - Urgent; XX – Today; XXX – Now or immediately

Abbreviations.

Nwamaka (2014); Adamu, Manu, Saadu & Isah (2020) & Bello (2024), all explained that there are common office abbreviations recognized in administration, more especially COEs. However, abbreviations may vary depending on the organization or industry. Therefore, it is always a good idea to clarify any unfamiliar abbreviations with your colleagues or superiors because nobody knows everything. It could be the simple abbreviations that you already know in every day work.

Characteristics and Features of Good Minuting

The following are some of the basic characteristics and features of good minuting in a file.

1. Setting the margin: Draw a margin of 1, 1.5 or 2 inches from the left hand side of the minuting sheet. This provides a good outlook of the document and allows your superior officer to make marginal note or comments when necessary (Adebayo, 2000 & ASCON, 2015).
2. There is also the need to leave space at the bottom of the page.
3. Minuting on typed written document: Adebayo (2000) opines that it is not tidy to minute on either the front or back page of a correspondence or memorandum received especially when such correspondence is typed written. This is to safeguard legibility of the document and ease of retrieval when need for further usage arises.
4. Addressing the recipient: The recipient is addressed at the top left side of the minuting sheet. The recipient is often addressed by the position he/she holds in the organization. Standard abbreviations are acceptable in addressing an officer when minuting. Common examples in the Polytechnic include: Rec. (Rector), D. Rec. (Deputy Rector), Reg. (Registrar), Bur. (Bursar), etc.
5. Page & Letter numbering: There are two major forms of numbering that should be maintained during minuting by any officer, they are as follows:

5.1 Page numbering: Every sheet of paper in the main file must be serially numbered for consistency and security of the documents. The numbering is preferred in red ink, at the top and center of the sheet. Attached bulky appendixes to a letter are often filed at the back cover (a.b.c).

5.2 Letter numbering: There should be a letter numbering when minuting to every addressee, the letter numbering comes at the top of the addressee's title/position. It is preferable to begin letter numbering with "A" (upper case) in red ink. It does not matter the rank, whoever is minuting for the first time on a fresh page should not use letter numbering while the second person can use letter "A" and then address the recipient. The next officer (after the second person) shall then use "B" and so forth.

i. When minuting below an already typed or hand written document, the initiating officer shall begin with letter "A".

ii. When minuting at the top of a document where there is no any typed or hand written text, the initiating officer needs not to letter number the minutes.

6. Responding to minutes: A minimum communication cycle is the one in which there is a sender – message – receiver and feedback. The feedback is a very vital aspect and constitutes the response or an answer to enquires. The following tips may be very useful: i. Do a research: Before responding to minutes, do a research by reading the contents of the letter, report, or memo on which you might have been asked to comment, advise, recommend or form an opinion. You may consult relevant past records to ascertain whether precedence has been set about the issue in question. ii. Cite relevant laws: Having gone through past records, an officer needs to ascertain whether the issue at stake relates to any law, rules, regulations or government circulars.

7. Closure of the minutes: An officer is expected to conclude the minutes by indicating the following: a. Append your signature or initial b. Write your designation and c. Date d. When minuting to a superior officer and it is observed that there is no more space for him/her to minute further, you should enclose a blank unnumbered sheet.e. Official minutes should not be sent to external organization.

8. Forwarding the minutes: The officer forwarding the minutes should observe the following tips:

a. Go to the cover page of the file. b. Write the designation of the addressee at the column marked "To". c. Write the page number where you minuted at the column marked "Page". d. Write the date at the column marked "Date". e. The file should be registered in an appropriate outgoing register before being dispatched to the addressee.

Don'ts in File Minuting

Kindly avoid the following while minuting: a. When minuting at the top of a document where there is no any typed or hand written text, the initiating officer should not letter number the minutes. b. The communicating officer should not begin a page with letter numbering. c. Never continue letter numbering from another page to another. d. Never number paragraphs with alphabets (a, b, c, etc). e. Never number the first paragraph. f. Never number the second paragraph with one (1), but with 2 (as it is assumed that the first unnumbered paragraph has a silent number 1) and g. Never differentiate the letter numbering of outside cover page and those of the inside page. h. Never leave what was addressed to you on the front cover uncrossed before you address to the next recipient. If you did not cross it, this means that you are yet to treat what was addressed to you. i. Never minute on the back of a page that there is an attachment.

Others include: J. Never minute before the signature, name and address of a writer of a communicator. k. Never deface a write up with minuting. l. Don't addressing the recipient with his name or qualification. m. The officer communicating should not end his minute without not writing his rank. (This is because this does not indicate ownership of the communication). n. The officer communicating should not end his minutes without not endorsing the communication. o. Never refuse to act on a file as directed to your desk is not only unethical, but an insubordination act to refuse to act on an official file designated for one's action. p. Never allow an undue delay to act on file as directed to your desk or withholding of files. q. Avoid any difference between the letter numbering inside page of file and the front cover letter numbering as this is an indication of a fraudulent unauthorized removal of a page or pages.

Dos in File Minuting

These includes: a. You should only letter number when minuting below an already typed or hand written document. As the initiating officer, you can begin with letter "A". b. The communicating officer should only begin a page with unletter numbered minuting. c. You can only begin a page with a fresh page with unlettered numbering. d. Number paragraphs with numbers (1,2,3, etc). e. Leave the first paragraph unnumbered. f. Number the second paragraph with 2 instead of 1. g. Always make sure that the letter numbering of outside cover page is the same with those of the inside page. h. Always neatly cross where it was addressed to you on the front cover before you address to the next recipient to indicate that you have treated what was addressed to you. i. Rather only minute on the back of the page of the attachment. j. Always minute after the signature, name and address of a writer of a communicator.

Others include: k. Always allow a write up to be free from minuting to make it free from defacing. l. Addressing the recipient with his title, rank or position the person holds in the organization. m. The officer communicating has to write his rank (as part of indication of ownership of the communication). n. The officer communicating has to endorse the communication (to indicate ownership of the communication). o. Always act on a file as directed to your desk is not only unethical, but an insubordination act to refuse to act on an official file designated for one's action. p. Always avoid undue delay to act on file as directed to your desk or withholding of files and q. The page numbering inside the file must correspond with the letter numbering on the front cover of the file.

File Minuting Communication Considered to be Fraudulent

According to Bello (2024), the following issues can constitute fraudulent activities in file administration:

- a. Any difference between the letter numbering inside page of file and the front cover letter numbering is an indication of a fraudulent unauthorized removal of a page or pages. The page numbering inside the file must correspond with the letter numbering on the front cover of the file.
- b. The filing officer and the communicating officer are not allowed to use eraser or suppression of records to correct any communication. This is to avoid doubts.
- c. The filling officer and the communicating officer are not allowed to use correction fluid to correct any communication or suppression of records.
- d. The communicating officer and the filing officer are not allowed to remove any page from the file page. Others include:
- e. The communicating officer and the filing officer are not authorized to exchange paged document in a file. Any difference
- f. The communicating officer and the filing officer are not authorized to alter any document in a file or falsify any record.
- g. The communicating officer and the filing officer are not authorized to cancel any document in a file.
- h. The communicating officer and the filing officer are not authorized to deface any written material in the file. This means not to minute on the face of the write up.
- i. The communicating officer and the filing officer are not authorized to hide files for personal reasons. Hiding an official file is unethical. File handlers should avoid doing that.

- j. Refusal to file a document due to a file. Just like it is unethical to refuse to act on an official file on one's table, it is equally unethical for an officer to refuse to file any official document in its appropriate file.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Administrative techniques or skills include organizational skills like organizing and maintaining filing systems, records, and databases, making phone calls and scheduling meetings, writing memos, letters, minuting and communications; communication skills like active listening skills, writing skills, speaking skills and reading skills; teamwork and Interpersonal skills like effective interaction skills; problem solving skills like ability to identify problems, ability to produce best solutions to the identified problem and confident decision making and communicating decision effectively; technology and software skills like using computer and internet; time management skills where you have to manage time effectively to be succeed respectively.

Minuting is considered as one of the most effective methods of organizational official written communication used in the day-to-day administration of an organization, especially in Colleges of Education. It is documented evidence that makes officials bound and responsible for their actions or inactions. Decisions are often reached through the minutes and directives for implementation are given.

This paper recommends that all administrators should acquaint themselves with the basic administrative skills as well as avoid the "don'ts" in minuting, as this has become a necessary art and science in bureaucracy and official communication across all cadres, disciplines and professions all over the globe.

References

- Adamu, I (2017), Forms of official communication in the civil service in Ogunlela, Y. I. (2017) Workshop in public administration a PAD 330 course of NOUN: Lagos: NOUN Press. www.nou.edu.ng
- Adamu, I, Manu, K, Saadu, B & Isa, S.G (2020), Minuting: A tool for Administrative communication. Published in Kano Journal of Vocational Education (KAJOVE) Vol. 5. No. 1 July 2020 ISSN: 1596-6712, A publication of Sa'adatu Rim
- Adetayo, A. A (2024) Sustaining professionalism in institutional administration through mentorship. Being keynote address presented at the second national conference of the Association of Nigerian Colleges of Education Professional Administrators (ANCOEPA) on Tuesday, August 26, 2024 at Federal College of Education, Osiele, Abeokuta. Pp 3-7.
- Adebayo, A. (2000). Principles and Practice of Public Administration in

Nigeria, 2nd edition, Nigeria, Spectrum Books Limited.

Adedayo, A. (2023). Managing Contemporary Issues in Institutional Administration– Challenges and Forte of Professional Administrators in Colleges of Education. Being keynote address presented at the maiden national conference of the Association of Nigerian Colleges of Education Professional Administrators (ANCOEPA) on Tuesday, August 22, 2023 at Federal College of Education, Osiele, Abeokuta. Pp 2, 5-7, 11.

ASCON (2015). 21st Bacth of Management Workshop for Senior Officers on Grade Level 13 in Kano State Public service, Participants' Manual, OHCS, Kano.

Bello, A.N. (2023). Being Association of Nigerian Colleges of Education Professional Administrators (ANCOEPA) BOT Chairman address at maiden national conference of the Association of Nigerian Colleges of Education Professional Administrators (ANCOEPA) on Tuesday, August 22, 2023 at Federal College of Education, Osiele, Abeokuta. Pp 2-3.

Bello, A. N. (2024). Etiquette of Communication in Tertiary Institutions Administration File Minuting to Eliminate Fraud Being Paper Submitted to the COEN International Journal of Higher Education Administration and Management. Pp 2-11

Bhagwan, V. and Bhushan, V. (2020). Public Administration. New Delhi: S. Chand. Pp1-2

Braji , I (2019), The need for effective communication skills in public service. In Arts and social Science research, vol. 9 (September, 2019) <https://fassjassr.com.ng>

Civil Service Manual, (2019). Handbook of the Office of the Head of Service, Kano State, Kano, Zashura Gen. Enterprises Ltd.

Gambo, K. & Manu, Y. A. (2021). Record Keeping in Nigerian Local Government. In Michael, A. I., Chika, A.C. and Paul, O.I. (Eds) *Topical Issues in Nigerian Local Government Administration*. Timex printing and publishing Company, Enugu, Enugu State, Nigeria .Pp 4-6
<https://www.un.org/en/academic-impact/capacity-building>

Gomez, L. F. & Dailey, S. L. (2019), Formal communication Retrieved on 24/01/2025 from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/314712165>. DOI:10.1002/9781118955567.wbieo083 San Jose State University

Jerry, C, Wofford, E, Gerloff, A. & Robert, C. (2002). Cummins, rganizational Communication,. New York: McGraw-Hill.

Kailes, J. & Enders, A. (2014). What is a Registry? <http://www.jik.com/d-rgt.html>, ik@pacbell.net. Pp 1-5

Keiling, H (2024), Administrative skills to build for professional growth. Retriewed on 24/01/25 From <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/asministrative-skill>

Msheliza, D.A (2024), The place, roles and expectations of professional

Administrators in unionism: balancing mandates, unionism and career life. Being Paper Presented at the 2nd national conference Association of Colleges of Education Professional Administration (ANCOEPA) at FCE, Abeokuta, Ogun State from 26-28 August, 2024.

Nwamaka, I.P. (2014) Introduction to administrative practices and procedures. In PAD 412 NOUN: Lagos p. 63.

Robert, B (2023), *Official communication* Retrieved on 25/01/2025 from <https://www.lawinsider.com/dictionary/official>

Sikri, R (2014), *Essentials of official communication* Retrieved on 25/01/2025 from <https://www.vedantu.com>

Wikipedia (2011), *Minuting and minutes writing*. UNILAG [http://stdc.unilag.edu.ng >wp-content>file:///C:/Users/USER/Documents/Minuting-and-Minutes-Writing-Version-3_SANYA.pdf](http://stdc.unilag.edu.ng/wp-content/file:///C:/Users/USER/Documents/Minuting-and-Minutes-Writing-Version-3_SANYA.pdf)s

Wikipedia (2024), *Organizational Communication*. Retrieved on 20/01/2025 from <https://en.wikipedia.org>